

1 **HPV E5 control of Pgbd5.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 The functions of the E5 gene of human papillomavirus remain incompletely defined. Some have described
7 partial transforming potential for E5 but only E6 and E7 are known to induce transformation through
8 inactivation of p53 and Rb1. We used transcriptomics here, measuring total transcription by
9 RNA-sequencing following artificial expression of E5 to identify putative E5 network targets and interaction
10 partners in human cells. We describe here activation of *Pgbd5* by the E5 protein of HPV16 and HPV84.

11 Citations

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